

STUDIES IN GLASS SYSTEMS: X-RAY ANALYSIS OF NaCl DISSOLVED IN B₂O₃-GLASS.

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The lattice distance of sodium chloride dissolved in boric oxide glass has been measured by Debye-Scherrer method, and is found to be 9.088Å, which represents more than 60% increase over the normal value. A theoretical explanation of the increase is given.

The properties of polar crystals in the crystalline state, in aqueous solution and in the gaseous condition have been investigated by different workers of the Fajans school (Fajans, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1934, B, 25, 103; *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1928, 34, 503; Wulff and Heigl, *Z. Kristallographie*, 1931, 77, 85; Wulff and Schaller, *ibid.*, 1934, A, 87, 53). Wulff and Majumdar (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1936, B, 81, 319) studied the mole refraction of the system $x\text{Na}_2\text{O}$, $y\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ and found that $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ in solid solution in B_2O_3 -glass is markedly deformed, the extent of deformation produced being of a much greater magnitude than in the corresponding aqueous solution. Zachariasen (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 3841) also studied similar systems and concluded that polar crystals in solid solution are present in the molecular as opposed to the ionic state in glass systems. Majumdar and Sarma (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 18, 241) have studied the systems $\text{XCl}-\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ at different concentrations and found that the deformation rule of Fajans holds good qualitatively in the case of solid solution of alkali halides in boric oxide glass, with the difference that the extent of deformation with cations of small diameter is much greater in glass than in aqueous solution or in crystal. Biltz, Weibke and Schraeder (Träger, *Z. anorg. und allg. Chem.*, 1937, 224, 253) on the other hand from a study of the data of previous workers, hold that the mole-refraction of simple glasses can be explained as equal to the sum of the refractions of the constituent oxides. Kordes (*Z. anorg. und allg. Chem.*, 1939, 241, 1, 478) on the other hand disputes this idea.

Biltz's contention may be true in the case of pure glasses; Majumdar and Sarma (*loc. cit.*) have proved that in the case of solid solutions of alkali halides in glass such additivity does not hold good, except with cations of large ionic diameter like Cs^+ , which is in complete harmony with the postulates of Fajans (Fajans and Joos, *Z. Physik*, 1924, 23, 1). It was therefore thought advisable to study the changes in the lattice distance of alkali salts, if any, caused by dissolving them in B_2O_3 -glass.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of the Samples.—Specially purified boric acid was dehydrated, first in a steam chamber for several hours in thin layers and finally in a vacuum desiccator until a portion dissolved in absolute alcohol did not give coloration with anhydrous copper sulphate. It was mixed with dry and pure sodium chloride in varying proportions and heated in a platinum crucible to 900°–1000° in an electric furnace for several hours until a homogeneous melt was obtained. The crucible was chilled and the solid taken out.

Analysis of the Samples.—A definite weight of the glass was taken in a weighed platinum crucible and treated repeatedly with a mixture of hydrofluoric and sulphuric acids and heated. The residue was weighed as sulphate. A second portion was dissolved in water and chlorine estimated volumetrically by a semi-micro method. In this way the stoichiometric ratio Na:Cl was determined. It was found that inspite of the precautions taken in the dehydration of the materials a certain amount of $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ had been formed. But a considerable amount of NaCl remained dissolved in B_2O_3 .

X-Ray Analysis.—Powder photographs were taken of the samples by the Debye-Scherrer method. The X-rays were produced by a demountable type of X-ray tube designed by Hadding. It consisted of a metal cylinder with a conical mouth at one end; to this a metal cone provided with a water circulating cooling device was fitted by means of Ramsay grease. This formed the anti-cathode. The cathode consisted of an aluminium disc with a concave surface from which the electron stream was focussed on the target below. A porcelain insulator insulated the high potential cathode from the metal parts. X-rays generated from the metal target left the tube through the openings covered with thin aluminium foils of thickness 0.0015 cm. fixed against the window faces by means of grease and tightened with the help of washers fitted with screws. Pure electrolytic copper was used as the anti-cathode and copper K-radiations were used throughout, $K\alpha_1$, $K\alpha_2$ and $K\beta$ being 1.537 Å, 1.541 Å and 1.389 Å respectively; $K\alpha$ was taken as the mean of $K\alpha_1$ and $K\alpha_2$, and equal to 1.539 Å.

The X-ray tube was evacuated to about 10^{-3} to 10^{-4} mm. pressure. This was secured by a two stage mercury pump (Leybold) backed by a Cenco rotary oil pump. The transformer, which was the source of high tension, was directly connected with the cathode without any rectifying device as the tube was self-rectifying. The tube was operated at 35-40 K.V. and 5-6 milliamperere current. The voltage applied to the primary of the transformer was regulated by means of an auto-transformer.

The X-ray beam coming out was made parallel by causing it to pass it through a series of slits. The latter was held in proper position by means of brass rings attached to metal base provided with levelling screws.

The film holder, which could slide against a groove in the metal base perpendicular to it, consisted of a rectangular brass frame with a brass lid at the back. The front portion was screened with a piece of black paper which could transmit X-rays. The plate holder could be fixed at any desired distance from the slit cap.

Pure NaCl crystal

FIG. 1

Pure $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ crystal

FIG. 2

NaCl (8.21%) dissolved in B_2O_3

FIG. 3

NaCl (7.98%) dissolved in B_2O_3

FIG. 4

The solid specimen under examination was first carefully ground in an agate mortar. A piece of zigzag paper was gummed to the slit cap by secotine and the fine powder was rubbed against the central part for exposure to the X-rays. The optimum thickness of the film would be given by the formula $t = 1/\mu$, μ is the mass absorption coefficient. By trial, however, the proper thickness was secured. The powdering was done in such a way that particles of the size 10^{-3} to 10^{-4} cm. diam. could be obtained.

TABLE ID.

NaCl (7.98%) dissolved in B₂O₃-glass (Fig. 4).

x	1.575	1.84	2.28	2.51	2.755	2.906	3.28	3.446	3.685
Nature	w	v.w.	s	v.w.	s	s	w	v.w.	s
x	4.11	4.52	5.08	5.46	5.95	6.52	6.91	7.13	7.6
Nature	v.s	s	s	w	s	w	v.w.	v.w.	v.v.w.

It is clear from Tables Ic and Id that the lines corresponding to Figs. 3 and 4 are almost identical.

For the purpose of calculation of the spacing the following trial method was adopted. The distance x between any pair of lines was measured and from equation (ii) the value of θ calculated. Sine of this angle was divided separately by $\sqrt{1}$, corresponding to (1,0,0) plane, $\sqrt{2}$, corresponding to (1,1,0) plane, $\sqrt{3}$, corresponding to (1,1,1) plane, $\sqrt{4}$, corresponding to (2,0,0) plane and so on and the values tabulated. As is compatible with theory, constant values will be obtained for NaCl corresponding to $\frac{\sin\theta}{\sqrt{1}}$, $\frac{\sin\theta}{\sqrt{2}}$, and so on. The mean of these values is taken. For NaCl, this constant works out for K_{β} (1.389 Å) to be 0.12645 and for K_{α} (1.539 Å) at 0.1409. From (i)

$$a_0 = \frac{\sqrt{(h^2 + k^2 + l^2)} \cdot \lambda}{\sin\theta} \quad \text{for the first order of reflection}$$

$$= \frac{\lambda}{2 \cdot \frac{\sin\theta}{\sqrt{(h^2 + k^2 + l^2)}}$$

Hence a_0 for NaCl with K_{β} works out

$$\frac{1.389 \times 10^{-8}}{2 \times 0.1264} = 5.495 \text{ \AA}$$

and with K_{α}

$$\frac{1.539 \times 10^{-8}}{2 \times 0.1409} = 5.465 \text{ \AA}, \text{ the mean value being } 5.479 \text{ \AA}, \text{ which}$$

is in fairly good agreement with the standard value 5.628 Å (Bragg, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1913, 89A, 246).

Considering the photographs in Figs. 3 and 4, we find in these some lines (e.g. $x=1.515, 1.48, 2.9, 3.44$, etc.) due to sodium borate. Eliminating these by comparing Figs. 3 & 4 with Fig. 2, we take the reflections corresponding to $\frac{\sin\theta}{\sqrt{4}}$, $\frac{\sin\theta}{\sqrt{8}}$, $\frac{\sin\theta}{\sqrt{12}}$, and so on. These must have originated from NaCl dissolved in the glass due to reflections from the planes (2,0,0), (2,2,0), (2,2,2), etc. The mean value of $\frac{\sin\theta}{\sqrt{(h^2 + k^2 + l^2)}}$ for K_{β} is found to be 0.0767 and that for K_{α} 0.0944.

Hence a_0 for NaCl dissolved in the glass corresponding to K_{α}

$$= \frac{1.539 \times 10^{-8}}{2 \times 0.0844} = 9.120 \text{ \AA}$$

and the value corresponding to K_{β}

$$= \frac{1.389 \times 10^{-8}}{2 \times 0.0767} = 9.057 \text{ \AA}, \text{ the mean value being } 9.088 \text{ \AA}.$$

The calculations of the other sample corresponding to Fig. 4 are not given in detail but it gives rise to almost identical value of spacing. This increase of about 60% of the lattice distance of NaCl when dissolved in a glass is very interesting and may be discussed from the theoretical standpoint.

It is well known that NaCl crystal is regarded as a polar lattice, *i.e.* sodium and chlorine are present in the ionic condition in the lattice forming what is called a face-centred cubical lattice. Born and Lande (*Verhandl. deuts. physikal. Gesellsch.* 1918, 20, 210) were the first to postulate the lattice theory of polar crystals. They enunciated the existence of two types of forces, electrostatic due to the mutual attraction and repulsion of the charges and a repulsive force between opposite charges operating within a *very short* distance. The potential energy of an isolated ion was calculated by considering the work that has to be expended in order to bring a similar ion from infinity to that point. These forces, electrostatic or otherwise, must be considered in three dimensions, along each of which there will be a divergent series involving a function of the spacing in the denominator, alternately positive and negative. By an ingenious method these authors have evaluated the series so that u may be represented by the formula

$$u = A.e.^2/a_0 + B/a_0^9,$$

where A is a numerical constant called the Madelung constant and B , a second constant due to the repulsive force. The value of π for the repulsive forces worked out to be 9 according to Born but a much lower value of the order of 5 was obtained by other workers.

The original theory of Born has undergone considerable modification. London (*Naturwiss.*, 1929, 17, 516), Lennard Jones and Taylor (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1925, 109, A, 476; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1937, 33, 8), Slater and Kirwood (*Phys. Rev.*, 1924, 23, 488; Born and Mayer (*Z. Physik*, 1932, 75, 1), Pauling (*Z. Krist.*, 1928, 67, 377) and others have introduced important modifications to the simple theory of Born. For example in the original theory the effect of the Van der Waals forces was neglected. But quite satisfactory agreement between experimental value of lattice energy of alkali halides and that calculated on the basis of the Born-Haber cycle has been obtained in the case of alkali halides. And it was only in the case of the II-group metals that the inadequacy of the treatment was recognised.

In their calculation of the potential of an isolated ion, Born and Lande have assumed the dielectric constant of the medium to be unity implying that there is no dielectric intervening the ions in the lattice. If on the other hand a dielectric medium intervenes, as in the present case, the potential of the ions will be altered as the electrostatic forces of attraction between oppositely charged ions will be diminished, the dielectric constant factor occurring in the denominator. For a lattice of the NaCl type, the potential is given by

$$u = -\frac{1.746 \cdot N_A \cdot e^2}{\epsilon_0} \quad \text{where } N_A = \text{Avogadro No. and } 1.746 = \text{Madelung const.} = A.$$

Taking the dielectric constant into consideration, the modified formula for the potential will be

$$u = A.e.^2/D.a_0 + B/a_0^9.$$

The dielectric constant of B_2O_3 -glass is known to be 3.5 (Thomas, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 36, 2109) and those of different borates lie between 6.44 and 7.50 (Landolt-Börnstein Tabellen, 1923, II, 1033). The effect of the dielectric on the repulsive forces, as well as on the Van der Waals forces will be comparatively small. The total effect of introducing an intervening medium of dielectric constant higher than unity will be therefore to decrease the Coulomb forces of attraction.

The direct outcome of this will be that the spacing will be increased, if the repulsive forces are not affected or at any rate not affected to the same extent as the electrostatic forces. There are theoretical reasons to believe that these short distance forces will not be affected to the same extent as the Coulomb forces by the new dielectric. If they were completely unaffected then the lattice distance would be increased much more than in the present case. But since the actual increase is about 66%, the repulsive forces must also be affected by the higher dielectric constant to a certain extent. And this is also true of the Van der Waals forces probably to a much smaller extent. Hence the deciding factor in the spacing of the lattice of a polar crystal dissolved in a medium is the dielectric constant of the medium. It would be interesting to compare the spacings of the same crystal dissolved in media of different dielectric constants, and experiments are in progress in this direction.

It may be suggested that the shifted lines are due entirely to different compounds. That some compounds are actually formed is shown by the complexity of the lines (Figs. 3 & 4). As has been pointed out, lines due to $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ are present both in Figs. 3 & 4, and these have been eliminated by comparison with Fig. 2. It is curious, however, that even after solidification of the fused mass, $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ should be present in the crystalline state in the solidified glass. This may be compared to the well known phenomenon of devitrification of glass. There is no evidence that a complex compound of chlorine with borates is formed, and moreover the strongest evidence that NaCl is present in the crystalline state dissolved in glass is that sharp lines are obtained from certain planes from which sharp lines emerge from the pure crystal as well.

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